
ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE DEMOCRACY IN NIGERIA: THE ROLES OF RULE OF LAW

By

Abubakar Abdurrahman Anas¹, Zahra Kyari Muhammad², Musa Ibrahim³,
& Faiza Bala Iliysu⁴

^{1,2,3} Kano State Polytechnic, & ⁴ Audu Bako College of Agriculture Dambatta

Abstract

Globally, the rule of law has been established as a central feature of modern states and democracies; it represents an ideal linked to political development. The rule of law rests on the idea that a society adopts through legislation a set of formal rules and norms and decides to adhere to those rules in order to regulate the behavior and interaction of individuals, public institutions and private organizations, including conflict resolution mechanisms. The study aims at achieving sustainable democracy in Nigeria: the roles of rule of law. Conclusively, characteristics of rule of law in Nigeria manifested that, the Nigerian 1999 constitution in its chapter iv on fundamental human rights integrates these rights into our principles of the rule of law. The characteristics of the rule of law are as follows: a) the legitimate authority empowered to make them makes the laws of the land. b) the laws are publicly declared and known to the community and must be obeyed by all. c) the laws apply to everybody so all persons are equal before the law including the lawgivers. d) members of the society are citizens and therefore have rights that must be protected by the law. e) that in applying the laws, discretion should not be applied but decisions should be based on the known principles of the law. f) that the laws apply proactively and not retroactively. Therefore, the rule of law is an affirmation of the principle that the governance of human society should be based on law rather than the whims and caprices of human beings. The paper offered the conceptual clarifications of achieving sustainable democracy in Nigeria: the roles of rule of law. it also highlighted the challenges relating to the rule of law in Nigeria and finally offered the following recommendations so as to enhance the rule of law, thereby drive good governance in the country as: there is need for increased commitment to constitutionalism and ensure that democratic principles are upheld at all times. Restructuring of government institutions is crucial to enhance the practice of rule of law. These include an independent judiciary, free and independent press, a strong civil society, and a professional and accountable police force.

Keyword: Sustainable Democracy, Rule of Law

Introduction

Globally, the rule of law has been established as a central feature of modern states and democracies; it represents an ideal linked to political development. The rule of law rests on the idea that a society adopts through legislation a set of formal rules and norms and decides to adhere to those rules in order to regulate the behavior and interaction of individuals, public institutions and private organizations, including conflict resolution mechanisms. This represents the basic social contract crystalizing a common aspiration of modern democracies. Rule of law include but not restricted to the following, “liberty”, equality before the law, “separation of powers, “Checks and balances”, “Social Justice”, Constitutional guarantee, and “enforcement of human and civil right”, “due process of law, independence of the judiciary, judicial review of executive and legislative actions (Obiagba, 2015).

In Nigeria, the rule of law is anchored on a Supreme Constitution which subjects all classes and persons including government and its agencies to its provisions. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) in section 1(1) states that “this constitution is supreme and shall have binding force on all authorities and persons throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria”. This suggests that everything must be done according to the law, which applies to all classes of persons. The Constitution also ensures fair hearing of trials in all cases, and guarantees the preservation of rights. In the recent time Rule of Law Index, published by the World Justice Project (WJP, 2023), Nigeria ranks 120th out of 142 countries scoring of 0.41 out of 10. Regionally, it ranked 23rd out of 34 countries in SubSaharan Africa (p.136). The index offers data organized into eight factors that encompass the concept of the rule of law, such as constraints on government power, absence of corruption, open government, fundamental rights, order and security, regulatory enforcement, civil justice, and criminal justice.

The Rule of Law is a concept in an array of ideologies that dominates liberal political morality: others include democracy, human rights, social justice, and economic freedom. The plurality of these values seems to indicate that there are multiple ways in which social and political systems can be evaluated, and these do not necessarily fit tidily together. Some legal philosophers insist, as a matter of analytic clarity, that the Rule of Law in particular must be distinguished from democracy, human rights, and social justice. They confine the focus of the Rule of Law to formal and procedural aspects of governmental institutions, without regard to the content of the policies they implement. But the point is controversial. As we shall see, some substantive accounts have been developed, which amount in effect to the integration of the Rule of Law with some of these other ideals as they are so tightly fused, and cannot be severed from each other in a practical sense. Indeed, the rule of law is the super-structure and life blood of every commendable democracy and as such, a sine qua non for the sustainability of democracy and good governance in any given state.

Concept of Rule of Law

The idea of rule of law is regarded as part of modern democratic governance. It protects the rights of all citizens and ensures that the government is accountable to the people. It also provides a framework for resolving disputes peacefully and fairly (Ojukwu, 2023). According to the United Nations (2008, p.1), the rule of law refers to a principle of governance in which all persons, institutions and entities, public and private, including the State itself, are accountable to laws that are publicly promulgated, equally enforced and independently adjudicated, and which are consistent with international human rights norms and standards. It requires, as well, measures to ensure adherence to the principles of supremacy of law, equality before the law, accountability to the law, fairness in the application of the law,

separation of powers, participation in decision making, legal certainty, avoidance of arbitrariness and procedural and legal transparency.

According to Dicey (1885), the rule of law consists of three inter-connected elements. Firstly, the rule of law means: absolute supremacy or predominance of regular law as opposed to the influence of arbitrary power, and excludes the existence of arbitrariness, or prerogative, or even of wide discretionary authority on the part of the government. Englishmen are ruled by the law, and by the law alone; a man may with us be punished for a breach of law, but he can be punished for nothing else.

This presupposes that no person should be subjected to punishment for a breach of a preestablished law, and the proper venue for determining whether such a breach of law has occurred is the courts. This principle has been guaranteed by the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in Section 36(12), and it has been long stated by the court in the case of *Aoko v Fagbemi* (1961) ANLR p.400. Thus, powers can only be exercised in accordance with written laws made by the legislature. Secondly, it means “equality before the

law, or the equal subjection of all classes to the ordinary law of the land administered by the ordinary law courts”. The rule of law in this sense excludes the idea of any exemption of officials or others from the duty of obedience to the law which governs other citizens or from the jurisdiction of the ordinary tribunals. This presupposes that no one is above the law and that everyone, including government officials, is subject to the same laws. It also means that the law is applied fairly and equally to everyone, regardless of their social status or wealth (United Nations, 2007). Thirdly, the rule of law means the recognition and enforcement of individual’s rights. This include a range of legal safeguards protecting individuals from arbitrary action taken by the government, with the courts empowered to act as the custodians of those safeguards (Valcke, 2012). The protection of civil and political rights is therefore an integral part of the rule of law.

Characteristics of Rule of Law in Nigeria

The Nigerian 1999 Constitution in its Chapter IV on fundamental human rights integrates these rights into our principles of the rule of law. Jibrin (2021) outlines the characteristics of the rule of law as follows:

- a) The legitimate authority empowered to make them makes the laws of the land.
- b) The laws are publicly declared and known to the community and must be obeyed by all.
- c) The laws apply to everybody so all persons are equal before the law including the lawgivers.
- d) Members of the society are citizens and therefore have rights that must be protected by the law.
- e) That in applying the laws, discretion should not be applied but decisions should be based on the known principles of the law.
- f) That the laws apply proactively and not retroactively. Therefore, the rule of law is an affirmation of the principle that the governance of human society should be based on law rather than the whims and caprices of human beings.

Conditions of achieve the rule of law

The United States Institute of Peace (USIP, 2009) outlines the necessary conditions to achieve the rule of law. These include just legal frameworks, public order, accountability to the law, access to justice and culture of lawfulness. Thus, the following essential points are crucial. Firstly, there must be laws that are consistent with international norms and standards. These laws must be certain, transparent, equitable and responsive to the entire population,

and not just the powerful elites. Secondly, public order is paramount to ensure that laws are enforced equitably, while the lives, property, freedoms, and rights of individuals are protected. It also involves reducing criminal and politically motivated violence and ensuring that criminal elements are pursued, arrested and detained. Thirdly, accountability to the law is important. This condition involves holding the population, public officials, and perpetrators of past conflict-related crimes legally accountable for their actions. It is also essential to have an independent judiciary free from political influence, and accountability mechanisms to prevent the abuse of power. Fourthly, access to justice is vital to ensure that citizens are able to seek and obtain a remedy for grievances through formal and informal institutions of justice that conform to international standards. These institutions must ensure equality, apply the law effectively, and ensure procedural fairness and transparency. Lastly, it is imperative to foster a culture of lawfulness. This allows the general populace to follow the law and address their grievances through the justice system.

Sustainable Democracy

Sustainable democracy is a kind of democratic governance that is stable, inclusive, and capable of enduring over time because it is rooted in the strong institutions, citizen participation, respect for human rights, and the rule of law. It is a form of democracy that can withstand challenges such as corruption, inequality, economic crises, and political conflicts while continuing to protect freedoms and deliver development.

The Rule of Law for Sustainable Democracy in Nigeria

Sustainable democracy can be achieved in the country through rule of law by ensuring that laws are supreme, fairly enforced, and respected by all. This includes leaders. When the legal system is impartial, rights are protected, corruption is punished, and power is limited, democracy becomes resilient and capable of lasting over generation to come.

Furthermore to achieve Sustainable democracy in the country there exists

- i. Independent judiciary
- ii. Equality before the law
- iii. Checks and balances
- iv. Transparent and fair elections
- v. Protection of human rights
- vi. Anti corruption measures
- vii. access to justice

Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper offered the conceptual clarifications of achieving sustainable democracy in Nigeria: the roles of rule of law. It also highlighted the challenges relating to the rule of law in Nigeria and finally offered the following recommendations so as to enhance the rule of law, thereby drive good governance in the country as:

1. There is need for increased commitment to constitutionalism and ensure that democratic principles are upheld at all times.
2. Restructuring of government institutions is crucial to enhance the practice of rule of law. These include an independent judiciary, free and independent press, a strong civil society, and a professional and accountable police force.
3. The justice system should be improved upon by providing adequate funding for the training of judicial personnel and ensuring strong partnerships with law enforcement agencies.

4. There is need to ensure protection of human rights, access to justice, and the promotion of diversity and inclusion. Awareness campaigns should be conducted to educate citizens about their rights and redress mechanisms available to them.
5. There is need to ensure transparency and accountability to fight against corruption and encourage public participation in governance.

References

- Aikuola, S. (2024, June 4). Attack on free press, harassment of journalist trail Tinubu's first year in office. *The Guardian*. <https://guardian.ng/attack-on-free-press-harassment-of-journalists-trail-tinubus-first-year-in-office/>
- Ayeni, V. (2024, May 5). Journalist detained on 'orders from above' spends fourth day in detention. *Punch*. <https://punchng.com/executive-repression-journalists-detention-adds-to-suppression-of-press-freedom>
- Banire, M. A. (2021, 28 September). *The challenges of the judiciary in contemporary Nigeria*. Paper Presented at the Annual Judges Conference of Ogun State Judiciary.
- Chidozie, P. (2024, May 12). Govt agents highest offenders as NHRC records 19,470 complaints of rights abuse. *Daily Post*. <https://dailypost.ng/2024/05/12/govt-agents-highest-offenders-as-nhrc-records-19470-complaints-of-rights-abuse/>
- Chilcott, J. (1998). Structural-functionalism as a heuristic device. *Anthropology and Education Quarterly*, 29(1), 103-111. 30 .ISSN Print: 2992-2763 – ISSN Online: 2992-4618 | Vol. 2, Issue 2, No. 1 / June 2024 <https://www.jopd.com.ng>
- Chukwuma, I. & Ebai, E. (2013). Promoting the rule of law through evaluation and performance measurement in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *World Justice Project*. <https://worldjusticeproject.org/news/promoting-rule-law-through-evaluation-and-performance-measurement-Nigeria-challenges-prospect>
- Colomy, P. (1986). Recent developments in the functionalist approach to change. *Sociological Focus*, 19, 139-158.
- Dicey, A. V. (1885). *Introduction to the study of the law of the constitution* (10th ed). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Durkheim, E. (1893). *The division of labour in society*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Glenda, A. (1996). Active learning in a constructivist framework. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 31, 349-369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00369153>
- Hornsby, A. S. (2015). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* (9th ed). Oxford University Press. International Monetary Fund. (2024). Nigeria: 2024 Article IV Consultation. IMF Country Report No. 24/102, May. <https://www.elibrary.imf.org/downloadpdf/journals/002/2024/102/002.2024.issue-102-en.xml>

- James, L. & van Zyl Smit, J. (2022, December 15). The rule of law: What is it, and why does it matter? *Constitution Unit*. <https://constitution-unit.com/2022/12/15/the-rule-of-law-what-is-it-and-why-does-it-matter/>
- Jibrin, I. (2021, April 28). *Setting benchmarks for enhanced security and national unity in Nigeria*. Paper Presented at Town Hall Meeting Organized by the Honorable Minister of Information and Culture, Lai Mohammed, at Kaduna State University <https://fmino.gov.ng/fgtownhallmeeting-setting-benchmarks-for-enhanced-security-and-national-unity-in-Nigeria/>
- Merton, R. (1949). *Social theory and social structure*. Free Press.
- Mo Ibrahim Foundation (2023). *2022 Ibrahim Index of African Governance – Index Report*. <https://mo.ibrahim.foundation/sites/default/files/2023-01/2022-index-report.pdf>
- National Bureau of Statistics. (2022). *Nigeria multidimensional poverty index, 2022*. NBS. <https://Nigerianstat.gov.ng/download/1241254>
- Okogbule N. S. (2005). Access to justice and human rights protection in Nigeria: Problems and prospects. *SUR –International Journal on Human Rights*, 3(2), 95-110. <https://sur.conectas.org/en/access-justice-human-rights-protection-Nigeria/>
- Olasunkanmi, A. (2018). Constitution without constitutionalism: Interrogating the African experience. *Arts and Humanities Open Access Journal*, 2(5), 272-276. <https://doi.org/10.15406/ahoaj.2018.02.00069>
- Olasupo, A. (2024, June 2). Restructuring, constitution amendment wont solve Nigeria's problems – Odinkalu. *Punch*. <https://punchng.com/restructuring-constitution-amendment-wont-solve-Nigerias-problems-odinkalu/>
- Omobola, D. (2023, October 2). Rule of law in Nigeria is weak – Ojukwu. *Vanguard*. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2023/10/rule-of-law-in-Nigeria-is-weak-ujukwu/amp/>
- Parkyn, G. W. (1977). Comparative education research and development education. *Comparative Education*, 13, 87-93. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305006770130104a>
- Parsons, T. (1977). *Social system and the evolution of action theory*. Free press. Punch. (2023, February 21). Disobedience of court threatens democracy. *Punch Editorial*. <https://punchng.com/disobedience-of-court-threatens-democracy/>
- Soyele, O. (2024, May 5). Judicial powers under threat: Disobedience of court orders becoming prevalent. *Leadership*. <https://leadership.ng/judicial-powers-under-threat-disobedience-of-court-orders-becoming-prevalent/>
- Spencer, H. (1896). *The principles of sociology* (vol. 3). Williams and Norgate. N.C. Obiagba, ideological Bases of the Nigerian Presidential constitutions (edited by Obidimma, Oraegbunam and Izunwa) Great-m Prints and ideas, Onitsha, 2015) p. 135. 1999 constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended)
- Oputa, C.A. The law and Twin Pillars of Justice, Government